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**Comparative Study On Effect Of Vermicompost And Chemical Fertilizers On
Yield And Yield Components Of Oryza Sativa**

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Rice is an important crop of poaceae family and a major food staple that is widely consumed all over the world. Inorganic and organic fertilizers are the main source of replenishing plants nutrient in agricultural soil. For the food production in ancient times, we use organic fertilizer but to compete the growth of population we are in a situation to change to chemical fertilizer. Researchers said that the use of chemical fertilizer decreases the crop yield due to soil acidification, decrease in biological activity in soil changes in soil physiological properties, so we have turned to organic farming. In my personal experience, In the 4 years of organic farming it is hard to take even the investment amount. It is an attempt to study both the effect of chemical fertilizer and vermicompost on *Oryza sativa*. The entire study was carried out in Palur, Trichy district, Tamil Nadu. The study occurs in the duration of September –14, 2020 to February – 10, 2021. The vermicompost plot is consider as plot-A and chemical fertilizer plot is considered as plot-B. The plot covers area of about 0.17 acre. The seed variety we have used is CO(R)50. In that plot-B shows good result than plot-A. Neither an inorganic fertilizer nor an organic fertilizer alone can result in sustainable reproductivity. By considering all the points we can make a new fertilizer chart for balancing both organic and inorganic fertilizer that is good to crop, soil and also our health, it should also yield profit. For growing population both organic and inorganic fertilizer are must.

Key words: Oryza sativa, vermicompost, chemical fertilizer, yield, population.